

On the Semantics of TPF-QS for Publishing and Querying RDF Streams at Web-scale

Appendix A: TPF-QS queries in CityBench

Ruben Taelman¹, Riccardo Tommasini², Joachim Van Herwegen¹,
Ruben Verborgh¹, Emanuele Della Valle², and Erik Mannens¹

¹ Ghent University – imec – IDLab, Belgium
{firstname.lastname}@ugent.be

² Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria, Politecnico of Milano, Italy
{firstname.lastname}@polimi.it

While *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS* allow custom windows to be defined over streams, *TPF-QS* always applies windows of one time unit wide. In this appendix, we explain a technique to create *TPF-QS* queries for *CityBench* that are semantically equivalent to the existing *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS* queries. That means that evaluation times for the three types of queries must be equal.

We chose an evaluation frequency 10 seconds since earlier experiments have shown that *TPF-QS* works best with this order of frequencies or slower, and it is a realistic query frequency for *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS*. Observations in the stream were therefore configured to be produced every 10 seconds.

For both *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS*, this evaluation frequency of 10 seconds was realized by applying window widths of 10s on each stream, which results in evaluation times every ten seconds. For *TPF-QS*, we consider time intervals $[m, m + 10s]$ for each observation, starting at observation time m as time annotation for *TPF-QS* streams. Since *TPF-QS* applies windows of one time unit wide with the default Mapping Expire strategy, this also leads to evaluation times every ten seconds. This technique results in equivalent evaluation times for the *c-SPARQL*, *cQELS* and *TPF-QS* queries¹ with semantically equivalent results.

As an example, Fig. 1 shows a timeline of observations with a frequency of 10s, where the windows and evaluation times for *c-SPARQL*, *cQELS* and *TPF-QS* are illustrated. The used *c-SPARQL* queries apply a time-based sliding window of width 10s and slide 1s, which results in the windows in Fig. 1a. Because *c-SPARQL* uses a Window Close, Non-empty Content policy, only the windows that end at a multiple of 10s will report results. *cQELS* applies the same time-based sliding windows of width 10s and slide 1s, which results in the same windows. Furthermore, *cQELS* uses the Content Change policy, which in this case results in the same evaluation times because the content also only changes at multiples of 10s, as can be seen in Fig. 1b. *TPF-QS* applies one-instant wide windows with a slide of 1 and a Mapping Expire policy. Since time intervals for each observation have a duration of 10s, the Mapping Expire policy leads to evaluation times every 10s, which results in the windows and evaluation times of Fig. 1c.

The evaluation times for *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS* are equal to each other, but they are one-off compared to those of *TPF-QS* for timestamp 0. This is because we assumed a $t^0 = 0$ for *c-SPARQL* and *cQELS*, while there in fact is no way to explicitly define t^0 for these engines. This is why we only consider the evaluation times after the first window to be of importance, when the effect of t^0 becomes irrelevant.

¹ Queries for the three approaches: <https://github.com/LinkedDataFragments/CityBench>

Fig. a: c-SPARQL time-based sliding windows with $\alpha = 10s$, $\beta = 1s$ and $t^0 = 0$.

Fig. b: cQELS time-based sliding windows with $\alpha = 10s$, $\beta = 1s$ and $t^0 = 0$.

Fig. c: TPF-QS time-based windows with $\alpha = 1s$, $\beta = 1s$, $t^0 = 0$ and the default Mapping Expire window policy.

Fig. 1: Comparison of time windows and evaluation times for c-SPARQL, cQELS and TPF-QS in the case of a stream that emits time-annotated statements every 10s. The windows that do not produce any results are indicated with as a thin line. Evaluation times are tagged underneath timestamps.